

SAFETY ASSESSMENT OF CHEMICALLY MODIFIED LIGNIN FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: *This study evaluates the safety implications of propionic acid–mediated lignin esterification intended to improve hydrophobicity and polymer compatibility. Lignin was esterified using propionic acid with sulfuric acid as catalyzer. FTIR and NMR confirmed successful ester bond formation through the appearance of characteristic carbonyl and alkyl signals, alongside reduction of hydroxyl-related peaks. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was employed to identify volatile and semi-volatile compounds in unmodified and esterified lignin, with toxicity classification via Cramer’s Decision Tree. Esterification altered lignin’s chemical profile, introducing new esters and transforming guaiacol-derived phenolics while degrading some volatiles. Most detected compounds belonged to Cramer Class I (low toxicity), but certain Class III substances, including diethyl sulfate (IARC 2A carcinogen), emerged after modification, likely due to acid-catalyzed side reactions.*

Keywords: food packaging, lignin, safety, barrier, coatings

1 INTRODUCTION

One promising candidate to be used as additive in food packaging applications is lignin, a natural aromatic macromolecule derived from lignocellulosic biomass. Its structure, however, varies across biomass types (softwoods, hardwoods, grasses), with differences in monolignol composition and linkages influencing reactivity and compatibility (Zhang et al. 2022). Lignin has attracted attention as a bio-based additive for coatings and films due to its antioxidant, antimicrobial, and hydrophobic characteristics, with potential enhancer of the functional performance of biopolymer-based coatings (Camargos et al. 2022), (Boarino e Klok 2023). Lignin can reduce oxygen and water vapor transmission, especially when the base material is hydrophilic, as lignin’s chemical structure contains hydrophobic groups, such as aromatic rings and methoxy (-OCH₃) groups, that repel water. However, lignin also contains hydrophilic groups, such as hydroxyl (-OH) and carboxyl (-COOH) groups (Marques et al. 2025; Zadeh et al. 2018). In hydrophilic matrices, these groups facilitate compatibility; however, for hydrophobic materials such as PBAT (which contains terephthalate units, aliphatic methylene groups, and ester bonds), the hydrophilic groups in lignin may hinder compatibility, necessitating lignin modification or the use of compatibilizing additives to improve compatibility (Boarino e Klok 2023). Several strategies can be employed to improve lignin compatibility on hydrophobic matrices, including esterification (Liu et al. 2019), acetylation (Sameni et al. 2017), grafting (Eraghi Kazzaz et al. 2019), compatibilizers (Han e Wu 2019), and physical modifications such as particle size reduction (Camargos

et al. 2022). These strategies have been shown to improve compatibility with hydrophobic matrices; however, many involve toxic reagents such as acid chlorides or anhydrides. Emerging strategies, such as esterification with organic acids offer safer, simple and sustainable alternatives (Liu et al. 2019). These modifications are considered less hazardous, although esterification may still introduce additional safety concerns, which are addressed in this study. This study investigates safety risks associated with esterification byproducts through chemical migration analysis using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Lignin esterification and characterization

Esterification was adapted from Liu et al. (2019). Kraft alkali lignin (CAS 8068-05-1) was reacted with propionic acid at a 1:7 lignin-to-acid ratio, with 10% (v/v) acetone to aid dispersion, and 5% (w/w) sulfuric acid relative to lignin as catalyst. The suspension was stirred for 3 h, then thermally treated in an autoclave at 121 °C for 4 h. The reaction mixture was washed repeatedly with distilled water and centrifuged at 4000 rpm until neutral pH, air-dried, and milled. Approximately 90% of the propionic acid was recovered by rotary evaporation and re-used for subsequent esterifications.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) - FTIR analysis of Lignin and E.lignin was carried out in a Bruker FTIR spectrometer ALPHA II (Bruker Corporation, Billerica, MA, USA) in transmission mode, operating at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The spectra were taken between 4000 and 300 cm⁻¹ by averaging 60 scans for each spectrum. All samples were scanned twice for verification purposes.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) - NMR analysis of Lignin and E.lignin was carried out. 1H–13C of cross-polarization/rotation at the magic angle (CP/MAS NMR) was obtained in a Bruker Avance III spectrometer of 9.4 T wide bore, with Larmor frequency of 400 MHz for 1H. A 4 mm dual-resonance MAS probe was used, operating at 400.1 MHz for 1H and 100.6 MHz for 13C.

Gas chromatography mass spectrometry analysis - Lignin and esterified lignin were analysed through GC-MS, to detect volatile compounds from these samples. Two extraction methods were used, *headspace and Liquid method*. Through headspace, about 25 mg of lignin and E.lignin were thermally treated at 200°C for 1 hour. Analysis was performed using a Zebron 5ms plus column (30 m × 0.25 mm ID × 0.25 µm), with a 1 mL injection volume. The injector was set to 250°C (split 1:10). The oven was programmed from 40 °C (5 min), ramped at 10 °C/min to 320°C. Mass spectrometry was conducted with electron ionization (EI) at 70 eV, scanning m/z 33–350. Compounds were identified using the NIST 2020, Version 2.4 library. In the *liquid Extraction Method* volatile compounds of lignin and E.lignin were extracted in 3 mL ethanol for 24 hours at 60 °C. A 1 µL aliquot was injected into the Zebron 5ms plus column under splitless mode (injector at 320°C, 0.75 min). The oven was programmed from 50 °C (3 min), ramped at 10°C/min to 320 °C, and held for 15 min. MS detection was carried out using EI at 70 eV, with full scan range 33–700 m/z. Identification was performed using the NIST 2020, Version 2.4 library.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lignin esterification

Esterification of lignin was performed to enhance its compatibility with the hydrophobic matrices. The process involved treating kraft alkali lignin with propionic acid under controlled heat (90–120 °C) to introduce ester functional groups. The reaction led to structural modifications, confirmed by FTIR (Figure 1). The first spectral change was the appearance of a strong absorption band around 1722 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C=O stretching in ester groups. This band is absent in native lignin and confirms the successful formation of ester bonds (Zhao et al. 2017). Additionally, bands observed at 2918 cm^{-1} and 2850 cm^{-1} represent asymmetric and symmetric C–H stretching, respectively, associated with the presence of propionyl alkyl groups (Sangeetha et al. 2022). Further changes were noted in the 1000–1300 cm^{-1} region, where alterations in C–O and C–O–C stretching vibrations were observed (Figure 1).

number	Peak/Change	Indication
1	2918 cm^{-1}	Propionyl alkyl group.
2	2850 cm^{-1}	Propionyl alkyl group.
3	1722 cm^{-1}	Ester bond formation.
4	1128 and 1030 cm^{-1}	Loss of hydroxyl groups.

Figure 1: FTIR spectrum of lignin and esterified lignin

Figure 2: ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR spectra of lignin and esterified lignin

The NMR spectra allowed detailed analysis of structural changes in lignin before and after esterification. Significant differences were observed in regions associated with aliphatic and carbonyl carbons, confirming the formation of ester groups. New resonances appeared at $\delta = 180\text{--}170$ ppm,

corresponding to aliphatic ester carbonyl carbons, and at $\delta = 28\text{--}26$ ppm and $\delta = 10\text{--}8$ ppm, corresponding to aliphatic carbon chains of the propionate groups. The aromatic region was unaffected, thus esterification mainly affecting aliphatic hydroxyl groups (Boarino e Klok 2023; L.-Y. Liu, Hua, e Renneckar 2019). As confirmed by both FTIR and NMR, lignin was successfully esterified using propionic acid. While absolute quantification was not possible with NMR, the significant reduction of signal intensity in the $\delta = 60\text{--}80$ ppm region (associated with aliphatic --OH carbons) indicates substantial esterification.

Safety of Lignin & E.Lignin

As observed above, esterification modifies the lignin structure, which can introduce chemical changes. For materials intended for food-contact applications, such modifications raise critical questions about the potential migration of toxic or uncharacterized substances into food (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids (CEF) 2016). Therefore, a thorough chemical safety assessment of E.lignin is essential to evaluate its suitability and regulatory compliance for use in sustainable food packaging. GC-MS analysis of lignin and E.lignin identified several compounds, which were classified according to their toxicity using Cramer's Decision Tree classification (Roberts et al. 2015). This system categorizes compounds into Class I (low toxicity), Class II (moderate toxicity), and Class III (high toxicity) based on their chemical structure.

Table 1: Major Compounds found in Lignin (GC-MS) and their toxic classification according to Cramer

Compounds	CAS	Chem class	Cramer	Peak change	Obs
4-Acetoxy-3-methoxyphenethyl alcohol, acetate	32022-28-9	Ester	Class I	Appeared	Ester formed
1,2,3-Propanetriol, tripropanoate	139-45-7				
Propanoic acid, ethyl ester	105-37-3				
Propanoic acid	79-09-4	Organic acid			
3-(4-Allyl-2-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2-propanediol	398-58-3	Phenylpropanoid			Esterification of guaiacol
4-Acetoxy-3-methoxyphenethyl alcohol, acetate	32022-28-9	Phenol and benzoate ester			Esterified phenolic compound
Naphthalene, 2,3-dimethoxy-	10103-06-7	Polycyclic aromatic ether			Detectable after esterification
Phenol, 4-(2-propenyl)- (4 Allylphenol)	501-92-8	Phenylpropanoid			
1-Hydroxy-2-butanone	5077-67-8	Hydroxyketone			
2,3-Bis[(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methyl]butane-1,4-diol, tetraacetate	41025-80-3	Phenylpropanoid			
3-Penten-2-one, 4-methyl-	141-79-7	Olefinic compound			
4-Penten-2-one, 4-methyl-	3744-02-3				
Diethyl sulfate	64-67-5	Ester			
Methanesulfonic acid, methyl ester	66-27-3				
Dimethyl sulfone	67-71-0	Sulfone			
Furfural	98-01-1	Furan derivative	Thermal degradation during esterification		
2,5-Furandione, 3-methyl-	616-02-4	Cyclic anhydride			
Furfural, 5-methyl-	620-02-0	Furan derivative			

Propanamide	79-05-0	monocarboxylic acid amide			Formed via condensation		
Guaiacol	90-05-1	Phenol	Class I	Decreased	Partially reacted to form 3-(4-Allyl-2-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2-propanediol		
2-Methoxy-4-vinylphenol	7786-61-0						
Benzenepropanol, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-	2305-13-7						
Phenol, 4-ethyl-2-methoxy-	2785-89-9						
Vanillin	121-33-5	Benzaldehydes					Possibly converted into 3,4-Divanillyltetrahydrofuran
(E)-3,3'-Dimethoxy-4,4'-dihydroxystilbene	7329-69-3	Stilbenol					Partially reacted to form 2,3-Bis[(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methyl]butane-1,4-diol, tetraacetate
Apocynin	498-02-2	Aromatic ketone					Esterified
Phenol, 2,6-dimethoxy-	91-10-1	Phenol					Possible conversion of phenolic OH during esterification.
trans-isoeugenol	5932-68-3	Essential oil					Reactivity of its allyl and phenolic groups.
2-Cyclopenten-1-one, 3-ethyl-2-hydroxy-	21835-01-8	Cyclic ketone			Class III		Partial esterification of the hydroxy group.
2-Cyclohexen-1-one, 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-(1-methylethyl)-	490-03-9						
1,4-Benzenediol, 2,5-dimethyl-	615-90-7	Hydroquinone	Class I	Disappeared	Volatilized or decomposed		
Coniferyl Alcohol ((E)-4-(3-Hydroxyprop-1-en-1-yl)-2-methoxyphenol)	32811-40-8	Phenylpropanoid			Conversion to 2,3-Bis[(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methyl]butane-1,4-diol, tetraacetate		
2-Hydroxy-gamma-butyrolactone	19444-84-9	Furan derivative			Esterified		
Octanal	124-13-0	Fatty aldehyde			Volatilized or decomposed		
1H-Pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde	1003-29-8	Pyrrole and Aldehyde	Class II		Volatilized or decomposed		
Cyclohexanone, 2-acetyl-	874-23-7	Cyclic ketone			Conversion or reactivity of the ketone group during esterification.		
Benzonitrile, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-(Dehydrodieugenol)	4421-08-3	Biphenyls	Class III		Reduced volatility or interaction during esterification		
3,4-Divanillyltetrahydrofuran	34730-78-4	Furan derivative	Class I	Increased			
Dehydroabietic acid	1740-19-8	Abietane diterpenoid	Class III		Conversion of abietic acid into its dehydrogenated form.		

Esterification of lignin markedly altered its chemical composition, forming new esters (e.g., diethyl sulfate, propanoic acid ethyl ester), transforming guaiacol-derived compounds, and degrading certain volatiles (Table 2). Guaiacol derivatives partially reacted to yield complex structures such as 3-(4-allyl-2-methoxyphenoxy)-1,2-propanediol, while coniferyl alcohol formed higher-molecular-weight phenylpropanoids. Thermal degradation produced furfural and other furan derivatives. Some phenolic

and guaiacol-based compounds decreased or disappeared, indicating esterification or volatilization (e.g., vanillin → 3,4-divanillyltetrahydrofuran; hydroquinone and coniferyl alcohol decomposed). Conversely, compounds like dehydroabietic acid increased, suggesting oxidative transformations. Most lignin compounds belonged to low-toxicity Class I, including vanillin, eugenol, creosol, benzenepropanol derivatives, and trans-13-octadecenoic acid, consistent with previous reports (Takada et al., 2004; Ehara et al., 2005; Lucejko et al., 2020). New Class III compounds—diethyl sulfate, methanesulfonic acid methyl ester, dimethyl sulfone, furfural, and 5-methylfurfural—appeared only in esterified lignin, indicating potential health concerns and the need for purification before food-contact use. Diethyl sulfate is classified as a Group 2A carcinogen (IARC, 1999). While esterified lignin is only 1% of PBAT coatings, migration studies are required to assess safety.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Lignin esterification with propionic acid successfully improved its hydrophobic character and as confirmed by FTIR and NMR. However, GC-MS analysis revealed that the modification altered lignin's chemical composition, generating new esters and transforming phenolic constituents. While most detected substances were classified as low toxicity (Cramer Class I), certain high-toxicity Class III compounds, including diethyl sulfate, were formed during esterification. These byproducts underscore the necessity for additional purification steps to ensure compliance with food-contact safety requirements. Overall, this study demonstrates that propionic acid-based esterification can be a viable route to enhance lignin performance in hydrophobic bio based coatings, after addressing the main safety concerns found.

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